

Pleomorphic Carcinoma in Transition to Papillary Carcinoma and Independent Mucinous Carcinoma of the Breast; A Report of the Rare Association

Takahiro Mase¹, Takeshi Hasegawa¹, Yoshimi Iriguchi², Masahito Nawa³ and Hideki Mori^{4*}

¹Breast and Endocrine Surgery, Ogaki Tokushukai Hospital, Japan

²Clinical Laboratory, Ogaki Tokushukai Hospital, Japan

³Nawa Clinic for Breast Oncology, Japan

⁴Division of Diagnostic Pathology, Ogaki Tokushukai Hospital, Japan

Citation: Takahiro Mase, Takeshi Hasegawa, Yoshimi Iriguchi, Masahito Nawa and Hideki Mori. Pleomorphic Carcinoma in Transition to Papillary Carcinoma and Independent Mucinous Carcinoma of the Breast; A Report of the Rare Association. *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour.* 2026;5(4):1-6.

Received Date: 30 March 2026; **Accepted Date:** 04 April 2026; **Published Date:** 08 April 2026

***Corresponding author:** Hideki Mori, Division of Diagnostic Pathology, Ogaki Tokushukai Hospital, Japan

Copyright: Hideki Mori, Open Access 2026. This article, published in *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour (ICMCRJ)* (Attribution 4.0 International), as described by <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

ABSTRACT

We report here a rare case of the breast of an elderly Japanese woman. The patient developed two nodules (A and B) in the left breast. The A nodule with a fibrous capsule constituted a pleomorphic carcinoma with bizarre giant cells and a well differentiated papillary carcinoma. The pleomorphic carcinoma was in transition to the papillary carcinoma suggesting that the pleomorphic carcinoma was transferred from the papillary carcinoma, possibly an encapsulated papillary carcinoma. Labelling index of Ki-67 of tumor cells of the pleomorphic carcinoma which consisted of a number of polyploid cells was much lower than the cells of the papillary carcinoma implying that some unknown etiology affecting cell cycle function such as through RB or p53 gene in the papillary carcinoma is an onset of the emergence of pleomorphic carcinoma in A nodule. The B nodule displayed the morphology of mucinous carcinoma with a large amount of extracellular mucin. At the periphery of the nodule, was also present another papillary carcinoma resembling that in A nodule. The mucinous carcinoma was also adjacent to the papillary carcinoma. It is assumed that development of the pleomorphic carcinoma and mucinous carcinoma is related to the papillary carcinoma in the two nodules. To the best of our knowledge, such case with three characteristic features of the breast carcinomas is extremely rare. Possible association and pathogenesis of these neoplasms is discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Pleomorphic carcinoma of the breast was first described by Silver and Tavassoli as an unusual high-grade phenotype of ductal carcinoma [1]. The carcinoma has been regarded as a rare pattern of high grade of “Invasive Breast Carcinoma (IBC) of No Special Type (NST)” characterized by a proliferation of pleomorphic and bizarre giant cells constituting >50% of the tumor cells in a back-ground of adenocarcinoma or adenocarcinoma with metaplastic spindle and squamous differentiation [2,3]. Pleomorphic carcinomas consist of many hyper-polyploidy cells. However, histogenesis of the pleomorphic carcinoma is not known. In general, polyploid cells emerge by skipping M phase of the cell cycle. It is also known that hyper-polyploid cells (>8n DNA content)

have lost long-term proliferation potential *in vitro* and *in vivo* [4]. Papillary carcinomas include papillary DCIS, Encapsulated Papillary Carcinoma (EPC), solid papillary carcinoma and invasive papillary carcinoma. Of them, only the EPC has surrounding capsule [5]. Meanwhile, Mucinous Carcinoma (MC) of the breast is an Invasive Breast Carcinoma (IBC) characterized by clusters of epithelial cells suspended in pools of extracellular mucin. MC is divided into type A and type B [6]. Type A MCs are relatively hypocellular, with a large amount of extracellular mucin, whereas type B MCs tend to be hypercellular and consist of large epithelial clumps or sheets that often show neuroendocrine differentiation. Pure MC requires a mucinous component of >90%; mixed MC has 10% to 90% [7]. We have come across a case of coexistence of pleomorphic carcinoma, papillary carcinoma and mucinous carcinoma of the breast of an elderly Japanese woman. These carcinomas were found in two different nodules. Pleomorphic carcinoma and papillary carcinoma were present in a nodule (A) with a fibrous capsule. Type A mucinous carcinoma was recognized in another nodule (B) which lacked surrounding capsule. In this report, relation of the two nodules and three characteristic features of the carcinomas is discussed.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 75-year-old Japanese woman noticed a mass in her left breast and soon visited a breast oncology clinic. She had medical care of diabetes mellitus and hypertension, although she had no previous history of malignant neoplasm. At the clinic, a hard mass approximately 8.0 cm in size and difficult mobility was confirmed. Nipple discharge was not present. Mammography revealed a high-density mass with unclear boundaries in the left upper-outer quadrant. The patient was referred to the Department of Endocrine Surgery of Ogaki Tokushukai Hospital for further evaluation of the breast mass. Ultrasonography performed at our hospital demonstrated two nodular lesions. Each size of the nodules was 48.9 mm × 33.3 mm × 24.7 mm and 37.3 mm × 28.3 mm × 22.6mm. Distance of each nodule was 8.7 mm (Figure 1). Macroscopic appearance of the two lesions after lumpectomy was shown in Figure 1. One nodule is surrounded by a thick fibrous capsule and another tumor nodule was rather cystic and bloody (Figure 1). Histologically, neoplastic cells of 30% of A nodule were arranged in micropapillary and cribriform patterns (Figure 2). Specific feature of the remaining neoplastic cells of 70% of the nodule was a proliferation of pleomorphic and bizarre multinucleated tumor cells. The giant cells constituting 50% of the tumor cells formed indistinct glandular structures (Figure 2). Both of neoplastic cells of the papillary and pleomorphic structure were crossing-over at the border of each tumor (Figure 2). Both of two carcinomas invaded fibrous capsule or connective tissues. No mesenchymal component such as fibromatosis or chondromyxoid matrix was not associated in the carcinoma. Strongly and diffusely positive for expression of ER was present in all neoplastic cells of the A nodule. However, expression of PR was rather variable. Mild expression of HER2 was recognized mainly in the papillary carcinoma. Labelling index of Ki-67 of cells in the papillary carcinoma was about 40%. Interestingly, that of cells in the pleomorphic carcinoma was around 10%. For the mucinous carcinoma in B nodule, both of ER and PR was strongly positive. Expression of HER2 was weakly positive, and index of Ki-67 was about 5%. In the present case, mucinous carcinoma was present in B nodule. Histologically, the mucinous carcinoma was type A with a large amount of extracellular mucin (Figure 2). At the periphery of B nodule, there was present a papillary carcinoma resembling that was seen in the A nodule. The papillary carcinoma was also adjacent to the MC. The mucinous carcinoma did not contain the micropapillary pattern like seen in the mucinous carcinoma with micropapillary features.

Figure 1: 1: Ultrasonography showing 2 structures with nodular lesions. Arrow means distance of the 2 lesions. 2: Cut surface of the tumor nodules at the mastectomy. Tumor nodule with fibrous capsule (left). Another tumor nodule with cystic and bloody appearance (right).

Figure 2: 3: A part of the papillary carcinoma with invasion to the fibrous capsule. 4: A part of the pleomorphic carcinoma with giant cells. 5: Mixed population of cells of the pleomorphic carcinoma and the papillary carcinoma the tumor cells. 6: A part of Type A mucinous carcinoma.

DISCUSSION

Papillary carcinomas consist of papillary DCIS, Encapsulated Papillary Carcinoma (EPC), solid papillary carcinoma and invasive papillary carcinoma [5]. Present papillary carcinoma in the A nodule resembles the EPC since the carcinoma is characterized by fine fibrovascular stalks covered by neoplastic epithelial cells surrounded by a fibrous capsule [7], although nuclear grade of the carcinoma is higher than ordinary EPC. In the present case, the pleomorphic and papillary carcinomas had a transition each other in A nodule. It is also reported that some of pleomorphic carcinomas are adjacent to DCIS or ductal carcinoma [1]. Thus, it is likely that the pleomorphic carcinoma was transferred from a papillary carcinoma, possibly, EPC. The pathogenesis of pleomorphic carcinoma is not known. Present observation will be a hint for understanding of the pathogenesis of the pleomorphic carcinomas of the breast. In this case, labelling index of Ki67 of neoplastic cells of the pleomorphic carcinoma were much lower than of the papillary carcinoma. The pleomorphic carcinoma contains a number of polyploid cells. These hyper-polyploid cells (>8n DNA content) have lost long-term proliferative potential [4]. Therefore, it is suggested that some unknown etiology affecting cell cycle function such as through RB or p53 gene in the papillary carcinoma may be an onset of the emergence of the pleomorphic carcinoma. It may be commonsense that both of the papillary carcinoma and pleomorphic carcinoma located in A nodule was not related to the occurrence of the mucinous carcinoma in B nodule. However, at the periphery of the B nodule, a small amount of papillary carcinoma resembling that in A nodule was present. Furthermore, the distance between the two nodules was less than 1cm. Thus, the tumor tissues in the two nodules might be connected in somewhere. Accordingly, it may be plausible that the papillary carcinoma was concerned the development of mucinous carcinoma as well as pleomorphic carcinoma. It is also known that pure MCs may have foci with a micropapillary pattern consisting of morula-like clusters suspended in tight mucin pools [8,9]. Morphology of the micropapillary seen in the pure mucinous carcinoma is not different from the papillary carcinoma recognized in the periphery of B nodule. Nevertheless, mucinous carcinomas are considerably concerned papillary carcinomas or carcinomas with papillary structures. We have reported a rare case of hypercellular cystic mucinous carcinoma with neuroendocrine differentiation accompanying a growth pattern of EPC [10]. In that study, only a small amount of intracellular mucin accumulation was identified by Alcian blue staining. This suggests that existence of some of mucinous carcinomas is over looked.

Author contributions

All authors have reviewed the final version to be published and agreed to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

Acquisitions, analysis, or interpretation: Hideki Mori, Takahiro Mase, Takeshi Hasegawa, Yoshimi Iriguchi, Masahito Nawa

Drafting of the manuscript: Hideki Mori

Critical review of the manuscript for important intellectual content: Hideki Mori, Takahiro Mase, Taheshi Hasegawa, Yoshimi Iriguchi, Masahito Nawa

Disclosures

Human subjects: Informed consent for treatment and open access publication was obtained or waived by all participants in this study.

Conflict of Interest: In compliance with the ICMJE uniform disclosure form, all authors declare the following:

Payment/services info: All authors have declared that no financial support was received from any organization for the submitted work.

Financial relationships: All authors have declared that they have no financial relationships at present or within the previous three years with any organization that might have an interest in the work.

REFERENCES

1. Silver SA, Tavassoli FA. Pleomorphic carcinoma of the breast: clinicopathological analysis of 26 cases of unusual high-grade phenotype of ductal carcinoma. *Histopathol.* 2000;36(6):505-14.
2. Rakha EA, Masuda S, Allison KH, et al. Invasive breast carcinoma of no special type. WHO Classification of Tumours, Breast Tumours. 5th edition. 2018;102-9.
3. Mase T, Hasegawa T, Kajiwara Y, Nawa M, Mori H. Metaplastic breast carcinoma with heterologous mesenchymal differentiation and carcinoma with pleomorphic pattern, A case report and review of literature. *Am J Surg Clin Case Rep.* 2024;8(2):1-5.
4. Vora S, Chatterjee S, Andrew A, Prasanna Kumar R, Proctor M, Zeng Z, et al. Aurora B inhibition induces hyper-polyploidy and loss of long-term proliferative potential in RB and p53 defective cells. *Cell Death Dis.* 2025;16(1):7
5. Brogi E, Troxell M, Horii R, et al. Papillary neoplasms: Introduction, WHO Classification of Tumours. Breast Tumours. 5th edition 2018;49-52.
6. Capella C, Eusebi V, Mann B, Azzopardi JG. Endocrine differentiation in mucoid carcinoma of the breast. *Histopathol.* 1980;4(6):613-30.
7. Wen Y, Desmedt C, Reis-Fiho JS, Schmitt F. Mucinous carcinoma. WHO Classification of Tumours, Breast Tumours. 5th edition. 2018:123-5.
8. Mac Grogan G, Collis LC, Lervill M, Rakha EA, Tan BY, Encapsulated papillary carcinoma. WHO Classification of Tumours, Breast Tumours. 5th edition. 2018;60-2.
9. Ng WK, Fine-needle aspiration cytology findings of an uncommon micropapillary variant of pure mucinous carcinoma of the breast; review of patients over an 8-year period. *Cancer.* 2002;96(5):280-8.
10. Mase T, Hasegawa T, Takagi C, Nawa M, Mori H. Hypercellular cystic mucinous carcinoma of the breast with a growth pattern of encapsulated papillary carcinoma. *Cureus.* 2025;17(10):e95549.